

SPC WITH ENABLE

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ABSTRACT: This paper describes a set of spreadsheets which perform the calculations necessary to plot control charts used in Statistical Process Control (SPC). The Enable Office Automation package was used to develop the spreadsheets. The SPC package is menu driven and includes on-line help. A full on-line manual provides program documentation. The following control charts are included: Individual and Moving Average / Moving Range Charts, X-Bar and Range Charts, Proportion Defective (p) Chart, Number Defective (np) Chart, Defects per Unit (c and u) Charts, and Weighted Defects per Unit (D) Chart. The paper describes each of the charts and tells how to select the correct SPC control chart for a given application. Completed charts and spreadsheets are also given.

SECTION I. INTRODUCTION: This section briefly describes the Enable Office Automation package that I used to write "SPC With Enable," defines SPC, and then explains how the rest of the paper is organized.

Enable: Enable is an integrated system consisting of separate modules for word processing, spreadsheets, data base and graphics. "SPC With Enable" uses only the spreadsheet and graphics modules and the menu generator from the master control module. I used the word processor to write the on-line manual. The manual was then converted from word processor files to a series of menu screens to allow the user to

move easily between pages without having to scroll through the entire document. In addition to the menus, the word processor files are included in the package for those who wish to print a hard copy of the manual. The Enable word processor can be used to print the entire manual (or portions of interest) without having to do "Screen Dumps" of the individual menus making up the on-line version of the manual.

SPC: The Department of Defense has defined SPC as follows:

"SPC is an element of a process improvement system which provides a method of statistically monitoring and controlling processes of manufacturing through the concept of 'continuous quality improvement.' The production process is first subjected to a process capability study. The results are then compared to specification requirements and used to develop an SPC plan. The plan directs operators, inspectors, and management when to periodically monitor predetermined product characteristics. Measurements are recorded and plotted on control charts. The control charts have computed 'control limits' which are drawn as upper and lower limit lines on the charts. The control limits are of assistance in judging the significance of variation of the process characteristic around the target value. Plotted points falling outside of the control lines are a statistical signal indicating that assignable causes have entered the process and the

process must be investigated.

"SPC helps distinguish between patterns of variation that are chance (random) and merit no investigation or assignable, indicative of trouble. SPC uses a group of statistical and problem solving techniques arranged in a logical sequence to provide a clear picture of where and why problems exist. With this information, managers can make the decisions necessary to solve these problems and make improvements in both product and process." [2]

Paper Organization: The next section of this paper describes the Main Menu of "SPC With Enable." The on-line manual is then discussed, and subsequent sections tell about each of the spreadsheets and the graph(s) or chart(s) that can be plotted from them. "SPC With Enable" will run under either DOS or Windows.

SECTION II. MAIN MENU: The SPC Main Menu allows you to select any of the spreadsheets which make up the package. The on-line manual can also be selected, and "Help" screens briefly describe each choice. The SPC Main Menu also allows you to quit the package and return to the computer's operating system, either DOS or Windows.

SECTION III. MANUAL: The on-line manual describes each of the charts included in the "SPC With Enable" package. Although a basic familiarity with SPC is assumed, the manual gives detailed instructions on how to enter data into each spreadsheet, and how to size and plot the charts after the data have been entered. The on-line manual is presented as a series of menu screens. Each screen allows you to move on to the next page if there is another page in that manual section. You may also go back one page if you're not on the first page of a section, or return to the Manual Table of Contents or to the SPC Main Menu.

One section of the manual tells how to decide which chart to use for a given application. This section serves as a refresher, or memory aid, for the user who already has some knowledge of the different types of control charts. It is not intended to be a tutorial on SPC control charts. The diagram shown below tells how to choose among the different control charts that are available. The diagram is in decision tree format. It is loosely based on a similar diagram from Pyzdek and Berger [5].

The eight "SPC With Enable" manual chapters which follow the chart selection section give detailed instructions for using each of the charts. I designed each chapter to stand alone by repeating information instead of referring the reader back to previous sections of the manual. The chapters are in the same order as the SPC Main Menu selections.

The next chapter of the manual gives general information about common plotting procedures. This section duplicates the plotting information given for each specific chart in its individual chapter. It serves as a quick reference for finding answers about the graphs.

The final chapter of the manual lists some references and tells you how to contact the author.

SECTION IV. X-Bar and R Charts:

There are two spreadsheets for creating X-Bar and R (Average and Range) charts. The two are identical, except one allows you to enter up to twelve values in each subgroup, and the other only allows six values. X-Bar and R charts are used with variable data. They are always used in pairs. The X-Bar chart detects out of control conditions in the average value of the variable while the R chart tells whether the within group variability is in statistical control. A major advantage of using variable data is that the quantitative nature of the information makes it easy to analyze. A disadvantage is that a different pair of charts is needed for every variable you wish to measure.

As you enter data into the spreadsheet, it automatically calculates the average of each data subgroup, the range, and the upper and lower control limits for both the X-Bar and the R

chart. The average of the averages (X-Double-Bar) and the average value of ranges (R-Bar) are calculated and used as the center line of the graph. The X-Bar chart control limits are found using the formula:

$X\text{-Double-Bar} \pm A_2 * R\text{-Bar}$. In this formula, A_2 is a constant which can be found in SPC reference tables. The upper control limit for the R chart is given by the formula $D_4 * R\text{-Bar}$, while the lower limit is found by the expression $D_3 * R\text{-Bar}$. Both D_3 and D_4 are constants which come from SPC reference tables. You should note that for subgroups of less than seven elements, D_3 is always zero, so the lower control limit for the R chart will be zero whenever the subgroup size is six or less. In all of the spreadsheets, whenever a lower control limit calculation results in a negative number, the spreadsheet assigns a lower control limit of zero. The control limit constants are designed so that the limits found by using them will lie three standard deviations away from the center line (X-Double-Bar or R-Bar) of the chart.

Once the data have been entered into the spreadsheet, all of the calculations for plotting the charts are done automatically. It is necessary, however, to size the graph before viewing or printing it. The Enable software allows you to set default values, but any time your graph size is different from the defaults, you'll have to set the size manually. The on-line manual contains the instructions for doing this.

SECTION V. Individual / Moving Average / Moving Range Charts:

If you have variable data but the subgroup size is one, the X-Bar and R charts have to be modified. Since there is only one data

element per subgroup, within group variability doesn't exist. We can simulate the required variability by finding the difference between adjacent data elements, thus giving a moving range which can be charted like the R chart. The moving average is also found by averaging adjacent data elements. Control limits can be found for both moving average and moving range charts just like the X-Bar and R charts above. The spreadsheet included in "SPC With Enable" lets you choose how many adjacent data elements you want to include, two or three. Using more data elements tends to smooth out the data, but it may also exaggerate the effect of an extreme data point since it will be used in more calculations.

In addition to the Moving Average, Moving Range charts, this spreadsheet also plots an Individual chart. It lets you see how the original data points look when charted against appropriate control limits. For three standard deviation limits, the constant multiplier is 2.66, which gives control limits of $\bar{X} \pm 2.66 * R\text{-Bar}$.

Although three standard deviation limits are acceptable for most SPC applications, since the subgroup size on this spreadsheet is one, there may be times when a more sensitive measure of out of control conditions is desirable. The spreadsheet allows you to choose two standard deviation limits instead of the normal three. This moves the control lines closer to the center line and makes the test more sensitive.

SECTION VI. Proportion Defective (p) Chart: The p chart is the first of the charts used for attribute data. Attribute data is any data which is presented in a "Yes / No" or "Pass / Fail" format. The p chart calculates and plots the proportion of items

in a sample which is defective.

The p chart is used to analyze attribute data given as the number of defective items in an inspection lot or subgroup. The p chart is widely used because of its simplicity and versatility. One big advantage of the p chart is that subgroups need not all be the same size. The main disadvantage would be that all types of defects are lumped together. The only thing you record is how many items had defects. You lose any information on the number of defects per item or the severity of the defects.

The p chart assumes that there is a constant probability of a defective item, so the control limits are calculated based on the binomial distribution. Given the center line, \bar{p} , the control limits are found by: $\bar{p} \pm 3 * \text{SQRT}[\bar{p} * (1 - \bar{p}) / n]$. Because the subgroup size (n) appears in the formula for computing the limits, the control limits change from subgroup to subgroup, but they are still located about three standard deviations from the center line.

SECTION VII. Number Defective (np) Chart: The np chart is used to analyze attribute data given as the number of defective items in an inspection lot or subgroup. The np chart is a variation of the p chart. In fact, the name np comes from multiplying the proportion defective (p) by the subgroup size (n) giving the number defective (np). Since it is a variant of the p chart, the np chart shares all of the p chart's advantages and disadvantages while adding one major restriction: all subgroups must be the same size.

SECTION VIII. Defects per Subgroup (c) Chart: The c chart is used to analyze attribute data given as a count of the number of defects in each inspection lot or sample

subgroup. The c chart counts the total number of defects found in each subgroup. One advantage of the c chart is that you record the number of defects, not just how many items were defective. This can be important when a certain number of defects is acceptable, or when you need to know how many defects each item has. The c chart has also found some applicability for inspecting continuous processes. The main disadvantages are that each subgroup must be the same size, and defects are lumped together with no concern for the severity of individual defects.

The c chart is based on the Poisson distribution. The center line, \bar{c} , is the total number of defects divided by the number of subgroups. Control limits are found by: $\bar{c} \pm 3\sqrt{\bar{c}}$. As always, a negative lower control limit is replaced by zero.

SECTION IX. Defects per Unit (u) Chart: The u chart is used to analyze attribute data given as a count of the number of defects per unit of product. The u chart relaxes the c chart's requirement that each subgroup be exactly the same size. The u chart records the total number of defects found in each subgroup along with the number of units in the subgroup.

The concept of a unit of product is important in understanding the u chart. A unit can be any meaningful measure which is taken as an inspection quantity. For example, in inspecting rope, a linear measure could be used, while the square meter might be used as a unit when inspecting cloth. In completing a u chart, you'll have to know how many defects were in each subgroup and also the number of units of product each subgroup contains. Like the p chart, the control limits of the u chart will vary from subgroup to subgroup. The

limits, once the center line \bar{u} is known, are calculated as: $\bar{u} \pm 3\sqrt{\bar{u}/n}$ where n is the subgroup size in units.

SECTION X. Weighted Defects per Unit (Demerit or D) Chart: The Weighted Defects per Unit (D) chart, like the c chart and u chart, is used to analyze attribute data given as a count of the number of defects per unit of product. Since my D chart is a modified u chart, it is different from the usual Demerit chart because I allow you to use different size subgroups. The D chart records up to six types or categories of defects found in each subgroup along with the number of units in the subgroup. The main advantage of the D chart is that you can assign different weights to each category of defect. This allows you to account for differences in severity of the different types of defect. When assigning weights to the different categories, you need to strike a balance between weighting severe defects so heavily that they overshadow the minor defects, and not weighting them enough, so they get lost in the clutter. The spreadsheet calculates a weighted sum of defects for each subgroup, then uses the subgroup size to calculate a weighted defects per unit value. Control limits are calculated and plotted for each subgroup.

SECTION XI. The Future of "SPC With Enable": "SPC With Enable" is presently available in the Beta Test version. Planned program enhancements include adding Process Capability computations to the variable data charts, increasing the number of subgroups allowed from thirty to fifty, and including the ability to clear the spreadsheet automatically.

REFERENCES:

[1] _____, Enable/OA Version 4.0, Enable Software, Inc. Ballston Lake, 1990.
 [2] _____, Defense Logistics Agency Manual 4155.2, Quality Assurance Program Manual for Defense Supply Centers, 1994.
 [3] _____, The Memory Jogger, A Pocket Guide of Tools for Continuous Improvement, Methuen, 1988.

[4] Pyzdek, Thomas, What Every Engineer Should Know About Quality Control, New York, 1989.
 [5] Pyzdek, Thomas and R.W. Berger, eds, Quality Engineering Handbook, Milwaukee, 1992.
 [6] Rickmers, Albert D. and H.N. Todd, Statistics, An Introduction, New York, 1967.

FIGURE 1: Average and Range (X-Bar and R) Charts

(a)

Enter data starting in cell B8. Use up to six cells for each subgroup. You should have at least 25 subgroups.

	6	6	7	12	2	6	7	7
Average (X-bar)	6.25	6.50	7.00	9.25	3.75	6.00	7.00	5.50
Upper Control Limit	8.59	8.59	8.59	8.59	8.59	8.59	8.59	8.59
X - Double Bar	6.41	6.41	6.41	6.41	6.41	6.41	6.41	6.41
Lower Control Limit	4.22	4.22	4.22	4.22	4.22	4.22	4.22	4.22
Subgroup Number:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Range (R)	4.00	3.00	0.00	6.00	4.00	2.00	2.00	3.00
Upper Control Limit	6.85	6.85	6.85	6.85	6.85	6.85	6.85	6.85
R - Bar	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00

(b)

X-Bar Control Chart

(c)

RANGE Chart

1(a). Spreadsheet that calculates averages, ranges, center lines and control limits. 1(b). X-Bar Chart. Note two out-of-control points. 1(c). R Chart.

FIGURE 2: Individual, Moving Average, Moving Range Charts

(a)

Date:	13	13	11	12	11	13
Data Element:	1	2	3	4	5	6
Moving Average (n = 2)	13.00	12.00	11.50	11.50	12.00	12.00
Moving Range (n = 2)	0	2	1	1	2	2
Moving Average (n = 3)	12.33	12.00	11.33	12.00	11.33	12.00
Moving Range (n = 3)	2	2	1	2	1	2
MOVING AVERAGE CHARTS						
Upper Control Limit (n=2)	10.75	10.75	10.75	10.75	10.75	10.75
X Double Bar: (n=2)	6.83	6.83	6.83	6.83	6.83	6.83
Lower Control Limit (n=2)	2.90	2.90	2.90	2.90	2.90	2.90
Upper Control Limit (n=3)	10.23	10.23	10.23	10.23	10.23	10.23
X Double Bar: (n=3)	6.70	6.70	6.70	6.70	6.70	6.70
Lower Control Limit (n=3)	3.16	3.16	3.16	3.16	3.16	3.16
MOVING RANGE CHARTS						
Upper Control Limit (n=2)	6.82	6.82	6.82	6.82	6.82	6.82
MR Bar (n=2)	2.09	2.09	2.09	2.09	2.09	2.09
Upper Control Limit (n=3)	8.90	8.90	8.90	8.90	8.90	8.90
MR Bar (n=3)	3.45	3.45	3.45	3.45	3.45	3.45
INDIVIDUAL CHART						
Upper Control Limit Ind	12.55	12.55	12.55	12.55	12.55	12.55
X Average	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00
Lower Control Limit Ind	1.45	1.45	1.45	1.45	1.45	1.45

(c) Moving Average Chart
n = 2

(d) Moving Average Chart
n = 3

2(a). Portion of the spreadsheet that calculates Individual, Moving Average and Moving Range Charts. Full spreadsheet for these charts has 24 data elements. 2(b). Individual Chart. 2(c). Moving Average, n=2 Chart. The Moving Average is computed by finding the average of two adjacent data points. 2(d). Moving Average, n=3 Chart. The Moving Average is computed from three adjacent data points. Note that the plotted data appears smoother as n increases, but the overall shape of the curve is the same in all three plots. Also note that the averaging process exaggerates the effect of extreme points by showing a whole range of out-of-control points instead of single points in the Individual Chart, but the out-of-control areas occur in the same portion of each chart.